

Heat Capacity and Thermodynamic Properties of Some Mixed Fluorides

H. V. KEER*, C. DEENADAS and K. C. BHAT

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay-400 076

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Heat capacities (C_p) of some mixed fluorides, having the composition $\text{KNi}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{F}_3$, where $x=0, 0.49, 0.69, 0.85$, were measured over the temperature range 80-300 K, using an isothermal calorimeter. $\text{KNi}_{0.85}\text{Zn}_{0.15}\text{F}_3$ and $\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3$ exhibited humps in their C_p vs T curves with maxima at 239.2 ± 0.2 K and 190.0 ± 0.2 K respectively, presumably corresponding to their Néel points. No anomalous behaviour in C_p was detected in $\text{KNi}_{0.49}\text{Zn}_{0.51}\text{F}_3$ and KZnF_3 . Thermodynamic functions, such as entropy, enthalpy and Gibbs free energy were evaluated between 80-300 K.

To estimate magnetic contributions to heat capacity, two methods, namely, Debye-Einstein (DE) and corresponding states (CS), were employed to determine lattice heat capacity. The values of enthalpy of transition for $\text{KNi}_{0.85}\text{Zn}_{0.15}\text{F}_3$ and $\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3$ were found to be 213 (DE), 231 (CS) and 148 (DE), 168 (CS) cal/mol, respectively.

A problem in magnetochemistry, which has attracted considerable attention in recent years, is the variation of thermal and magnetic properties, especially in the region of the ordering temperature of a ferromagnet (T_C) or an antiferromagnet (T_N), as the system is diluted by substitution of a non-magnetic component. One of the interesting series of compounds has been '3d' metal double fluorides of the type KMf_3 , where $M = \text{Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, etc.}$ Since these compounds crystallize in the cubic perovskite structure, they are ideally suited for the study of 180° superexchange in the antiferromagnetically ordered state below room temperature. Many workers¹ have measured the magnetic susceptibility and reported on the antiferromagnetism of these compounds, the Néel temperatures being about 88 K (KMnF_3), 114 K (KCoF_3), 275 K (KNiF_3) and 243 K (KCuF_3), respectively. Corresponding heat capacity peaks were reported by us² at 83.3 K, 109.5 K, 253.5 K and 233.2 K respectively.

The present communication deals with heat capacities and thermodynamic properties of $\text{KNi}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{F}_3$ ($x=0, 0.49, 0.69, 0.85$) compounds over the temperature range 80-300 K. This study was undertaken to investigate the effect of random substitution of paramagnetic nickel by diamagnetic zinc ions on the Néel temperature and to estimate thermodynamic parameters, including those associated with magnetic order-disorder transition.

Experimental

The samples for calorimetric measurements were prepared by the method reported in the literature³. Analysis of X-ray powder diffraction photographs indicated that the solid solutions, $\text{KNi}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{F}_3$, possess cubic perovskite structure at room temperature, the respective lattice constants being 4.04 \AA ($x=0$), 4.02 \AA ($x=0.49$), 4.00 \AA ($x=0.69$) and 3.98 \AA

($x=0.85$). The values of x , obtained from chemical estimation of nickel using the conventional dimethylglyoxime method, were in good agreement with the results of X-ray analysis.

The details of the construction and operation of the isothermal calorimeter employed in the heat capacity measurements have been described elsewhere^{4,5}.

Results and Discussion

Smoothened heat capacity curves have been depicted in Fig. 1. The average scatter of the observed C_p values from their own mean was about 1-2%.

Fig. 1. Heat capacities of $\text{KNi}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{F}_3$ compounds.
1. KZnF_3 2. $\text{KNi}_{0.49}\text{Zn}_{0.51}\text{F}_3$
3. $\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3$ 4. $\text{KNi}_{0.85}\text{Zn}_{0.15}\text{F}_3$

$\text{KNi}_{0.85}\text{Zn}_{0.15}\text{F}_3$ and $\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3$ exhibited humps in their C_p vs T plots with maxima at

239.2±0.2 K and 190.0±0.2 K, respectively, presumably corresponding to their Néel points (T_N). Since KNiF_3 reveals a peak³ in C_p at 253.5 K, it is evident that magnetic interactions are weakened by random replacement of paramagnetic nickel by diamagnetic ions, whereby the length of the interacting chain is decreased. On the otherhand, magnetic studies on the same compound have shown^{2,6} a peak in magnetic susceptibility (χ) at about 280 K. The difference between T_N and the temperature at which the maximum in χ occurs needs an explanation. KNiF_3 crystallizes in a cubic perovskite structure which is an extremely close-approximation of a 3-dimensional nearest neighbour only Heisenberg system. It can, therefore, be assumed that the anisotropy is very small. Dipolar contributions cancel because of the cubic symmetry which is retained also at low temperatures⁷. Further, the above argument is strengthened by the findings of Yamaguchi and coworkers⁸ who showed that the next nearest neighbours interactions are only 5×10^{-2} th of the nearest neighbour interaction. One, therefore, expects from this model a difference of the order of 10% between T_N and the temperature at which the maximum in χ occurs. Our experimental finding satisfactorily confirms this theoretical prediction⁹. Further, the presence of magnon or magnon-type of excitations in the paramagnetic region has been predicted by Marshall¹⁰ on the basis of the spin-wave theory. Even in the absence of long-range ordering about T_N , there will exist regions of correlated spins as a consequence of the short-range order.

No anomalous behaviour was detected in $\text{KNi}_{0.49}\text{Zn}_{0.51}\text{F}_3$ and KZnF_3 . Considering the excitations of a 3-dimensional disordered Heisenberg antiferromagnet within the framework of a Greens function, Janes and Edwards¹¹ estimated the critical concentration, C , of spins at which the system ordered magnetically to be equal to 0.34. Therefore, on the basis of our heat capacity measurement, $\text{KNi}_{0.49}\text{Zn}_{0.51}\text{F}_3$ should reveal magnetic ordering below 80 K which is the lower limit of temperature measurements.

Thermodynamic properties such as entropy, S° , enthalpy $H^\circ - H_0^\circ$, and Gibbs free energy $(G^\circ - H_0^\circ)/T$, were evaluated between 80-300 K. For this purpose, extrapolation of C_p values below 80 K was made using the following functions :

$$\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3 : \\ D(96/T) + 2E(260/T) + 2E(505/T) (80 - 130 \text{ K} ; \pm 1\%)$$

$$\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3 : \\ D(95/T) + 2E(260/T) + 2E(480/T) (80 - 300 \text{ K} ; \pm 1\%)$$

$$\text{KNi}_{0.49}\text{Zn}_{0.51}\text{F}_3 : \\ D(93/T) + 2E(265/T) + 2E(480/T) (80 - 200 \text{ K} ; \pm 0.5\%)$$

$$\text{KZnF}_3 : \\ D(90/T) + 2E(270/T) + 2E(425/T) (80 - 300 \text{ K} ; \pm 1\%)$$

The respective values at a few selected temperatures have been listed in Table 1. The values for

$x=0.49$ are likely to be in error, if a magnetic transition exists below 80 K.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF $\text{KNi}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{F}_3$ COMPOUNDS (1 cal = 4.184 J)

T/K	C_p° cal/K mol	S° cal/K mol	$H^\circ - H_0^\circ$ cal/mol	$-(G^\circ - H_0^\circ)/T$ cal/K mol
$\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3$				
80	12.0	(9.25)†	(432)†	(3.85)†
100	14.5	12.20	698	5.23
200	25.2	25.60	2688	12.15
300	27.5	36.80	5449	18.64
$\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3$				
80	12.1	(9.35)†	(4.36)†	(3.89)†
100	14.7	12.35	705	5.30
200	25.4	26.44	2808	12.40
300	27.5	37.05	5433	18.94
$\text{KNi}_{0.49}\text{Zn}_{0.51}\text{F}_3$				
80	12.3	(9.39)†	(4.84)†	(3.97)†
100	14.9	12.43	707	5.36
200	23.8	25.89	2701	12.39
300	27.5	36.44	5314	18.73
KZnF_3				
80	12.6	(9.64)†	(445)†	(4.08)†
100	15.4	12.76	726	5.50
200	24.3	26.57	2768	12.73
300	27.6	37.25	5413	19.21

† Figures within the parentheses are extrapolated values.

The following methods were employed to estimate the lattice heat capacity and entropy and then the corresponding magnetic contributions in $\text{KNi}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{F}_3$ ($x=0.69, 0.85$) compounds :

(i) *Debye-Einstein (DE) method* : A combination of Debye-Einstein functions, used for extrapolation of heat capacities below 80 K, was assumed to represent the lattice heat capacity when extended upto 300 K. It was further assumed that $C_p \sim C_v$. The magnetic heat capacity and the associated enthalpy of transition (ΔH) could then be determined.

(ii) *Corresponding states (CS) method* : Since the system $\text{KNi}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{F}_3$ crystallizes in the cubic perovskite structure and formula weights of the concerned compositions do not differ widely, it may be assumed that the vibrational contributions to entropy and heat capacity of these compounds obey a law of corresponding states. Then, S (lattice) = $\phi(T/\theta)$ and C_p (lattice) = $(T/\theta) \phi'(T/\theta)$ where ϕ is the same function for KZnF_3 , $\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3$, $\text{KNi}_{0.69}\text{Zn}_{0.31}\text{F}_3$ and θ is a characteristic temperature, different for each compound. The method of calculation was analogous to that employed by Stout and Catalano¹¹ for isostructural MF_3 compounds. The values of r ($\text{KNi}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{F}_3$, S) evaluated around 300 K were found to be 0.94 and 0.92 for $x=0.69$ and 0.85, respectively. The values of enthalpy of transition for $x=0.69$ and 0.85 were determined to be 148 (DE), 168 (CS) and 213 (DE), 231 (CS) cal/mol, respectively.

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